

The Study of the Saponins of *Albizzia lebbek* Benth Seeds from Madhya Pradesh*

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Albizzia lebbek Benth seeds from Madhya Pradesh yield a mixture of two saponins, Lebbekanin A and Lebbekanin B and free sucrose. Lebbekanin A is present in major quantity and is the saponin of echinocystic acid while Lebbekanin B is the saponin of oleanolic acid and is present in minor quantity. Both the saponins contain the same four sugars, glucose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose as sugar moieties. The 16 α -nature of the hydroxyl group in echinocystic acid is shown to be responsible to bring about its isomerisation to albigenic acid in ethanolic hydrochloric acid hydrolysis.

The well defatted seeds of *Albizzia lebbek* Benth collected from the local campus on alcoholic extraction and subsequent usual treatment¹ yielded a mixture of three products as shown by thin layer chromatography (one major and two minors). One of the minor constituents was identified as free sucrose. The mixture has been separated by column chromatography on silica gel using chloroform : methanol : water (65 : 35 : 10) as eluent and the fractions giving the same spots on T.L.C. were combined yielding two distinct T.L.C. pure saponins (one major and one minor). This mixture of saponins was also separated by preparative T.L.C.

The saponin present in major quantity on hydrolysis with aqueous sulphuric acid (7%) yields an acid saponin m.p. 310–12°, acetate m.p. 268–70° and was identified as echinocystic acid (I) by T.L.C., I.R. spectra and mixed melting point with authentic sample. The sugars obtained by the hydrolysis have been identified as glucose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose and the saponin has been named as *Lebbekanin A*.

The second saponin isolated in the small quantity on sulphuric acid hydrolysis gives a triterpenic acid m.p. 305–07°, acetate m.p. 263–65° and has been identified as oleanolic acid (II) by T.L.C., I.R. spectra and mixed melting point with authentic sample. This also gave the same four sugars, glucose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose as obtained in case of *Lebbekanin A*. It has been named as *Lebbekanin B*.

The *Lebbekanin A* on hydrolysis with ethanolic hydrochloric acid yielded a mixture of two triterpenic acids which have been identified as echinocystic acid (I) and albigenic acid (III). The latter was earlier reported to be a new acid and not an isomerisation product². On the other hand when the same saponin *Lebbekanin A* when hydrolysed with

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1. I. P. Varshney, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 446.

aqueous sulphuric acid gave only echinocystic acid (I), indicating that during the hydrolysis by ethanolic hydrochloric acid, echinocystic acid (I) has been transformed into albigenic acid (II) by the shifting of a double bond from 12-13 position to 13-18 position. In an attempt to assign the reason for the transformation of echinocystic acid (I) into albigenic acid (III), T.L.C. pure samples of oleanolic acid (II), acacic acid (IV), echinocystic acid (I), machaerinic acid (V), and cochalic acid (VI) have been heated separately with ethanolic hydrochloric acid and also with aqueous sulphuric acid under the same conditions as used for the hydrolysis of the saponin. It has been found that in both the cases all these acids remain untransformed except echinocystic acid which partly transforms into albigenic acid (III) in the case of ethanolic hydrochloric acid and not with aqueous sulphuric acid. The only difference in the structure of these acids is that echinocystic (I) has got 16α -hydroxyl group while cochalic acid (VI) and acacic acid (IV) have 16β -hydroxyl group and do not transform in contrast to echinocystic acid (I) which is 16α -hydroxy. Therefore this leads to the conclusion that it is the 16α hydroxyl group which is responsible to bring about this transformation in the case of ethanolic hydrochloric acid hydrolysis and the aqueous sulphuric acid is a better hydrolysing agent for the saponins.

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